

MODELING BLAST FAILURE OF FIBRE METAL LAMINATES

E. Sitnikova¹, Z. W. Guan^{2,4*} and W. J. Cantwell³

¹ Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK
Email: Elena.Sitnikova@nottingham.ac.uk

² School of Engineering, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK
Email: zguan@liv.ac.uk, Webpage: <https://www.liv.ac.uk/engineering/staff/zhongwei-guan/>

³ Aerospace Research and Innovation Centre (ARIC), Khalifa University of Science, Technology and Research, Abu Dhabi, UAE
Email: wesley.cantwell@kustar.ac.ae

⁴ School of Architecture and Environment, Sichuan University, Chengdu 610065, PR China

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ABSTRACT

Fibre metal laminates (FMLs) are multi-layered materials based on stacked arrangements of aluminium alloy and fibre-reinforced composite materials. Currently, FMLs such as GLARE (glass fibre/aluminium) and CALL (carbon fibre/aluminium) are attracting the interest of a number of aircraft manufacturers. For example, GLARE is being used in the manufacture of the upper fuselage of the A380, an aircraft that is capable of carrying up to 700 passengers. However, with such composite materials being more widely used, an on-going concern is the effect of foreign object impacts and blast on their mechanical properties. An example of impact is that of an aircraft underbelly or wing impacted at high velocity during take-off and landing by stones and other small debris from the runway. In addition blast can also occur in aircraft due to accident or terrorist attack. Composites undergo either impact or blast likely suffer both internal and external damages. In this paper, 3-D nonlinear finite element models were then developed to simulate blast failure of FMLs. Here, the effort was concentrated on modelling woven glass fibre reinforced composites, as simulation of aluminium alloys is relatively simple. In the current work, a damage evolution law is incorporated into the composite constitutive behaviour to obtain the blast response of FML panels. The implementation of the composite failure model into Abaqus/Explicit through a user-defined subroutine is discussed and validated. Also, the approximation of the blast impulse expressed by a surface pressure function is discussed and the limitations of this approximation are specified. The model is validated against the experimental results. Finally, summary remarks are drawn to highlight the major outcomes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-metal laminate (FML) is a hybrid laminated structure consisting of alternating layers of metal and fibre-reinforced composite. The advantages of FMLs are high strength/weight ratio, cost-effectiveness, versatile stacking sequence, and good fatigue, impact, fire and corrosion resistance. FMLs are suitable for aerospace applications ([1], Vogelesang and Vlot, 2000).

Recently, the numerical study by Vo et al. ([2], 2013) on blast loading of FML panels based on four different aluminium alloys indicated the similar conclusions for non-perforation failure modes. Langdon et al. ([3, 4] 2007a,b) undertook an experimental study of the effects of the localized blast loading on the thin and thick FML panels. They observed a large variety of failure scenarios in relation to perforation and non-perforation failure modes. In particular, the tests showed that in thick panels with a high proportion of composite material, one of the principal failure mechanisms was extensive

debonding of the back face aluminium layer, where the debonding area was increasing with the increase of impulse.

One of the commonly employed approaches for the numerical analysis of FML failure is through finite element modelling by using the commercially available software packages. In these types of models, each of the FML constituent materials is assigned an appropriate material behaviour ([5] Karagiozova et al., 2010; [6] Mohamed et al., 2012). However, modelling the constitutive response of the composite is not fully established due to the complexity of damage initiation/evolution, strain-rate dependence and failure mechanisms in these materials. Many of the composite failure models are based on the plane-stress state material response in accordance with the classical laminate analysis. This can be a limitation in modelling the through-thickness impact damage ([6] Mohamed et al., 2012), when high compressive stresses occur in the material.

In the current work, the most common aspects of the dynamic failure in fibre reinforced composites, namely, 3D constitutive behaviour, damage initiation/evolution and rate-dependent characteristics are incorporated in a relatively simple continuum mechanics based model. The formulation is applicable for the composites with a plane weave architecture, which is more appropriate for use in structures under impact loading as it provides a better impact resistance than the unidirectional or cross-ply composites ([7] Kim and Sham, 2000).

This paper presents a further development of the previous modelling efforts on simulating the experimental blast behaviour of FML panels ([3, 4] Langdon et al., 2007a,b). The modelling the perforation failure in thin FML panels was based on work carried out by Sitnikova et al. ([8] 2014), where instant failure of the composite material was assumed. In the current work, an updated composite failure model with a damage evolution law is incorporated into the composite constitutive behaviour and the blast response of FML panels is simulated. Firstly, the material models of the FML constituents are introduced, and the implementation of the composite failure model into Abaqus/Explicit [9] through a user-defined subroutine is discussed and validated. Then, finite element modelling of the FML panels is described, the approximation of the blast impulse expressed by a surface pressure function is discussed and the limitations of this approximation are specified. The numerical predictions are validated against the corresponding experimental results, with reasonably good correlation.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Modelling of the dynamic response of aluminium alloys is relatively simple, as John-Cook plasticity and damage criterion are available in most of commercial finite element codes. The only challenging task in modelling FMLs is to simulate damage of fibre reinforced composite layers under high strain-rate loading.

2.1 Constitutive models for glass fibre reinforced composite

The woven glass fibre reinforced composite (GFRP) material is modelled as an orthotropic linear elastic material up to the onset of damage. Table 1 shows the material properties.

Table 1: Composite material properties [5].

ρ (kg/m ³)	E_1, E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}, ν_{13}	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{23}, G_{13} (GPa)
1800	13	4.8	0.1	0.3	1.72	1.69

The modelling of damage is based on the continuum damage mechanics approach which was first introduced by Kachanov ([10] 1958), who proposed to use a scalar quantity called damage variable for quantifying the accumulation of dissipated damage in isotropic materials. As the damage grows, the damage variable increases from zero to unity, where zero value describes the virgin material, while the value of unity defines complete material failure. In case of anisotropic material, the damage

accumulation can vary in different directions, and in order to account for damage non-uniformity in such cases, damage tensor (D), instead of scalar variable, is commonly used. Presence of the damage makes the material weaker, and in order to account for the influence of damage on the stress state, the effective stresses are defined, which are related to the true stresses as follows:

$$\hat{\sigma} = D\sigma, \quad \sigma = [\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{33}, \sigma_{12}, \sigma_{23}, \sigma_{31}]^T, \quad \hat{\sigma} = [\hat{\sigma}_{11}, \hat{\sigma}_{22}, \hat{\sigma}_{33}, \hat{\sigma}_{12}, \hat{\sigma}_{23}, \hat{\sigma}_{31}]^T \quad (1)$$

The strain at the onset of damage in the material is defined as:

$$\varepsilon = S^0 \hat{\sigma} = S^0 D\sigma = S\sigma, \quad (2)$$

where S is a compliance tensor for the damaged composite and S_0 the undamaged one. The degraded material stiffness components are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= E_1^0(1 - d_1), \quad E_2 = E_2^0(1 - d_2), \quad E_3 = E_3^0(1 - d_{3c}), \\ G_{12} &= G_{12}^0(1 - d_{12}), \quad G_{23} = G_{23}^0(1 - d_2), \quad G_{13} = G_{13}^0(1 - d_1). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{12} &= \nu_{12}^0(1 - d_1), \quad \nu_{13} = \nu_{13}^0(1 - d_1), \quad \nu_{23} = \nu_{23}^0(1 - d_2) \\ \nu_{21} &= \nu_{21}^0(1 - d_2), \quad \nu_{31} = \nu_{31}^0(1 - d_{3c}), \quad \nu_{32} = \nu_{32}^0(1 - d_{3c}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where the d_i are the damage variables, namely, d_1 and d_2 correspond to the failure in warp and weft fibre directions, respectively, d_{3c} describes through the-thickness composite crushing failure, and d_{12} refers to the in-plane shear failure. Here, d_1 and d_2 take different values at tension and compression and are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} d_1 &= 1 - (1 - d_{1t})(1 - d_{1c}), \\ d_2 &= 1 - (1 - d_{2t})(1 - d_{2c}), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the subscripts "t" and "c" denote tensile and compressive failure, respectively.

The damaged stiffness matrix C can be obtained by inverting the damaged compliance matrix S , and therefore, the stress-strain dependence of the damaged material becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{31} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{33} \\ \varepsilon_{13} \\ \varepsilon_{23} \\ \varepsilon_{31} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= E_1(1 - \nu_{23}\nu_{32})\Delta, \\ C_{22} &= E_2(1 - \nu_{13}\nu_{31})\Delta, \\ C_{33} &= E_3(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})\Delta, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{12} &= E_1(\nu_{21} + \nu_{31}\nu_{23})\Delta, \\
C_{23} &= E_2(\nu_{32} + \nu_{12}\nu_{31})\Delta, \\
C_{13} &= E_1(\nu_{31} + \nu_{21}\nu_{32})\Delta, \\
C_{21} &= E_2(\nu_{12} + \nu_{13}\nu_{32})\Delta, \\
C_{31} &= E_3(\nu_{13} + \nu_{12}\nu_{23})\Delta, \\
C_{32} &= E_3(\nu_{23} + \nu_{31}\nu_{13})\Delta, \\
C_{44} &= G_{12}, \\
C_{55} &= G_{23}, \\
C_{66} &= G_{13},
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\Delta = 1/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21} - \nu_{23}\nu_{32} - \nu_{13}\nu_{31} - 2\nu_{21}\nu_{32}\nu_{13}) \tag{8}$$

This above formulation needs to be supplemented by damage initiation criteria and damage evolution law in order to fully describe the failure in the composite.

2.2 Failure criteria for glass fibre reinforced composite

The criteria for damage initiation are a set of conditions, which, once satisfied, trigger the evolution of the damage. Six failure conditions similar to those proposed in ([11] Gama et al., 2001) are considered in order to account for various failure modes. Tensile-shear failure criteria similar to ([12] Hashin, 1980) fibre failure criteria were used to describe damage initiation conditions as below.

In warp and weft fibre directions:

$$f_{1t} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{\sigma_{1t}^r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{\sigma_{12}^r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{31}}{\sigma_{31}^r}\right)^2 - 1 \geq 0, \quad \sigma_{11} > 0, \tag{9}$$

$$f_{2t} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{\sigma_{2t}^r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{\sigma_{12}^r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{23}}{\sigma_{23}^r}\right)^2 - 1 \geq 0, \quad \sigma_{22} > 0. \tag{10}$$

Compressive failure in the warp fibre direction:

$$f_{1c} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{\sigma_{1c}^r}\right)^2 - 1 \geq 0, \quad \sigma_{11} < 0, \tag{11}$$

Compressive failure in the weft fibre direction:

$$f_{2c} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{\sigma_{2c}^r}\right)^2 - 1 \geq 0, \quad \sigma_{22} < 0, \tag{12}$$

Through-the-thickness crushing failure:

$$f_{3c} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{33}}{\sigma_{3c}^r}\right)^2 - 1 \geq 0, \quad \sigma_{33} < 0, \tag{13}$$

In-plane shear failure:

$$f_{12} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{\sigma_{12}^r}\right)^2 - 1 \geq 0, \tag{14}$$

In Eqs. (9) – (14), σ_{ij}^r ($i,j = 1t, 1c, 2t, 2c, 3c, 12, 23, 31$) are the material strengths.

Rate dependence for strengths in warp and weft directions is defined as follows

$$\sigma_{ia}^r(\dot{\varepsilon}_{ii}) = \sigma_{ia}^s \left(1 + R_1 \ln \frac{|\dot{\varepsilon}_{ii}|}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right), \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (15)$$

where $R_1 = 0.02$ is a strain-rate constant, and index "a" indicates tensile or compressive failure mode. The expressions for through-the-thickness strength and shear strengths have the same form, however a smaller value of strain rate constant, $R_2 = 0.01$, has been applied.

$$\sigma_{3c}^r(\dot{\varepsilon}_{33}) = \sigma_{3c}^s \left(1 + R_2 \ln \frac{|\dot{\varepsilon}_{33}|}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^r(\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}) = \sigma_{ij}^s \left(1 + R_2 \ln \frac{|\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}|}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right), \quad ij = 12, 23, 31 \quad (17)$$

2.3 Damage evolution

Based on a damage evolution model proposed by Iannucci ([13]2006). With the onset of failure, the damage variable increment for the corresponding failure mode is calculated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{d}_{1t} &= \alpha_1 \left(\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{\sigma_{1t}^r} \right)^2 - 1 \right), \quad \text{if } f_{1t} \geq 0, \Delta\varepsilon_{11} > 0, \\ \dot{d}_{1c} &= \alpha_1 \left(\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{\sigma_{1c}^r} \right)^2 - 1 \right), \quad \text{if } f_{1c} \geq 0, \Delta\varepsilon_{11} < 0, \\ \dot{d}_{2t} &= \alpha_1 \left(\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{\sigma_{2t}^r} \right)^2 - 1 \right), \quad \text{if } f_{2t} \geq 0, \Delta\varepsilon_{22} > 0, \\ \dot{d}_{2c} &= \alpha_1 \left(\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{\sigma_{2c}^r} \right)^2 - 1 \right), \quad \text{if } f_{2c} \geq 0, \Delta\varepsilon_{22} < 0, \\ \dot{d}_{3c} &= \alpha_2 \left(\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{33}}{\sigma_{3c}^r} \right)^2 - 1 \right), \quad \text{if } f_{3c} \geq 0, \Delta\varepsilon_{33} < 0, \\ \dot{d}_{12} &= \alpha_2 \left(\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{\sigma_{12}^r} \right)^2 - 1 \right), \quad \text{if } f_{12} \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Coefficients α_1 and α_2 in the above equation govern the rate of growth of damage variable. The damage variable is updated at each time increment using the following expression:

$$d_{ab}(t_{n+1}) = d_{ab}(t_n) + \dot{d}_{ab}\Delta t, \quad ab = (1t, 1c, 2t, 2c, 3c, 12), \quad (19)$$

The progressive failure model introduced in the previous sections was implemented into the main Abaqus program through a VUMAT subroutine. The subroutine is called to perform iterative calculations of the constitutive response of composite layers within the finite element model for FMLs.

A quarter of the FML panel was modelled, with appropriate symmetry and boundary conditions applied as shown in Fig. 1. The aluminium layer thickness of 0.6 mm and thermoplastic interlayer thickness of 0.05 mm (assumed) were kept constant for all the FML lay-ups. The composite ply thickness was calculated by subtracting the total aluminium and cohesive layer thickness from the measured average panel thickness and dividing it by the number of composite plies. The 3D constitutive behaviour was considered for all the constituent materials, hence 8-noded solid elements with reduced integration (C3D8R) were used to mesh aluminium layers and composite plies, while the cohesive layers were

meshed using COH3D8 elements. A biased mesh was generated outside the central 60x60 mm area of the panel, where a finer mesh size of 1x1 mm was used. A “rough friction” surface interaction was defined between the aluminium and composite layers on both the exterior and interior faces of the contacting layers to address possible contact after the cohesive layer fails [8].

Figure 1: FE model of A3T22 panel: (a) symmetry and boundary conditions; (b) in-plane mesh; (c) through the thickness mesh.

The spatial pressure distribution and the pulse time history are shown in Fig. 2, which are implemented into the modelling through user-defined loading conditions.

Figure 2: Spatial pressure distribution and time history.

3 MODELLING RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the FE models developed together with the constitutive and damage behavior of the constituent materials, blast responses related to a number of loading cases were calculated for different FML lay-ups. To validate the accuracy of the numerical predictions, a comparison with the experimental results [3, 4] was made. Four blast loading cases were calculated for the A2T12 FML lay-up. Figs 3 (panel cross-sections) and 4 (rear face views) show comparisons of displacement contour plots with the experimental data and. In all four loading cases, perforation failure was predicted, which is consistent with the experimental data. The rupture and outward petalling around the circumference of the perforation hole was captured in the front and back face aluminium layers. Also, the FE simulations predict more extensive failure areas for larger impulses, and this behaviour is consistent with the experimental observations.

Fig. 5 presents the comparison of predicted deformation modes of A4T32 FML lay-up with tested panels in two loading cases. As can be seen, at a lower pulse, $I = 9:06$ Ns, there is good agreement between the experiment and simulation, both qualitatively and quantitatively. However, at a higher impulse, $I = 10:3$ Ns, when perforation failure occurred, the calculations once again predict a larger perforation zone than that observed experimentally. Similar results are obtained for A4T34 FML

Figure 3: The predicted (left) and experimental (right) displacement contour plots for A2T12 FML panels over a range of the blast impulses.

Figure 4: The back face pedalling failure from the numerical prediction and the experimental data.

Figure 5: Numerically predicted and tested cross-sections of the FML panel A4T32 subjected to two blast loads.

panel, for which also two loading cases were considered. A comparison of panel cross-sections in Fig. 6 reveals that for this lay-up, multiple debonding occurred between the aluminium and the composite layers. This behaviour was predicted in the calculations, and the failure modes were predicted correctly, namely, large inelastic deformations on the back panel at $I = 14:65$ Ns, and perforation failure at $I = 16:63$ Ns. A comparison of the back face deformation modes in Fig. 7 shows that the predicted diamond-shaped back face deformation pattern is similar to that observed in the experiment.

Finally, a comparison of the numerical failure predictions with the experimental results for panel A4T36 at $I = 20:41$ Ns is shown in Fig. 8. For this FML, and also for the other panels with multiple aluminium layers and thick blocks of GFRP, large back face debonding occurred, which was captured by the calculations. All of the material layers, except for the back face aluminium sheet, were perforated, and the model predicts this. However, the size of the failure zone at the blast face is larger than that observed experimentally.

Figure 6: Comparison of the cross-sections of the deformed A4T34 FML panels.

Figure 7: The predicted back face maximum principal strain contour plot with the experimental result for the A4T34 panel lay-up at $I = 14.65$ Ns.

Figure 8: Comparison of the calculated contour plots with the experimentally observed failure of FML panel A4T36 at $I = 20:41$ Ns. Plots (a), (c) - cross-section view; (b),(d) - back face view.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Finite element modelling of the panels based on various stacking configurations has been carried out using the commercial software package Abaqus/Explicit. Relatively simple continuum mechanics based material model for the composite constituent has been proposed and implemented into the main program through a user-defined subroutine. The model incorporates 3D constitutive behaviour, a damage evolution law and rate-dependency of the composite material. The formulation proposed is applicable to composites with a plane weave architecture, as well as with possible through thickness damage. The numerical predictions have shown that the model captures the observed deformation and damage in the panels with a high degree of accuracy. Particularly respect to the perforation mode, various types of failure have been captured, such as back face aluminium petalling, extensive tearing and debonding between the aluminium and composite layers. The models developed may be used to undertake parametric studies that cover varieties of FMLs made with various constituent materials.

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